

Original Research Article

Assessment of Nurses Practices Regarding Intramuscular Injection among Adult Pakistani

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Abstract

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The aim of this study was to assess nurse's practices of intramuscular (IM) injection. The key concept of this study was to identify the correct and incorrect practices according to checklist. Nurses play a significant role in healthcare delivery system. Nurses are practicing IM injection that is highly considered evidence based practice and application of skills. For IM injection, it is necessary to select the proper site of injection, angle of needle insertion and aspiration according to proper guidelines. An observational study was conducted from February 2002 to April 2020. The study population was 156 registered nurses and student nurses. Data was collected through observational checklist which was scored as 0 = incorrect and 1 = correct. Chi square test was used to check the association between registered nurses and student nurses. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect sample. Significant association found between the practices of registered nurses and student nurses. Checklist for IM injection was correctly followed by majority of nurses and few nurses did not follow accordingly. The study findings explored that there was significant association between nurses regarding administration of IM injection. Due to small sample size the results of this study cannot be generalized. Secondly, it is short time duration for the study.

Keywords: Checklist, Intramuscular injection, Nurse, Practice

INTRODUCTION

In health care delivery system, nurses play a significant role like protocols of treatment, assessment, nursing care to the patient and handling of other injuries. Nurses perform multiple skills their health care setting Gatchel (2018). In clinical setting, the nurse's performance should be effective for patient recovery. The nurses are practicing IM injection that highly considered evidence based practice and application of skills. For IM injection, it is necessary to select the sit of injection, angle of needle insertion, and aspiration according to proper guidelines (Greenway, 2015).

The purpose of health care providers is to administer the injection to protect lives and save health. Through observation the practices are monitor properly and controlled well. The inappropriate practices of IM injection

cause adverse effects and injury to the client (Yusefzadeh, Didarloo et al., 2018).

In nursing profession, the psychomotor skill is very important activity with significant consequences. The best practices of IM injection improve the quality of nursing care but also maintain nursing standards at clinical setting. IM injection is a nursing practice and significantly important to provide better care and relief to the patients and facilitate to them. The important duty for nursing procedure is to perform accurately (Alawadi, 2017).

The safe practices of IM injection require the use of safety needles. It reduces the pain of injection and minimizes the risk of needle-stick injury. The size of needle is measured in gauges (diameter of the needle). The 21G needle is used commonly but the selection of

needle depends on the viscosity of the drug to be injected. Before giving the IM injection, ensure that needle used for injection is sharp that reduce the pain. The Public Health England (2013) recommends 23G or 25G needle for IM vaccines. The needle length depends on: (a) Muscle mass (b) Patient's weight (c) Amount of subcutaneous fat (Shepherd, 2018).

There are almost 12 billion injections administered annually worldwide. For mostly injections, the IM route is preferred over the intravenous and subcutaneous routes due to the increased vascularity of muscle tissue and the corresponding increase in the bioavailability of drugs when administered intramuscularly. As like sedative medicine, antipsychotic therapies, hormonal medicine and vaccine are administered through IM route. This is beneficent way to provide drug absorption (Soliman, Ranjan et al., 2018).

In developing countries, about 16,000 million injections are administered per year. Above 90% injections are given for therapeutic purpose and on other hand 5-10% injection given as preventive treatment. Injections are one of the most common psychomotor skills in health care setting throughout the world. It is a complex psychomotor job that needs skill and knowledge on the part to perform this technique. For IM injection the most preferred sites is into the deltoid and/or gluteal muscle (Srividya, Nagabushan et al., 2015).

Prevalence of obesity is increasing day by day and injection which is administered for the purpose of drug administration cannot reach to the muscle. Evidence based clinical practice explores that body mass index (BMI) calculated before administering IM injection which is helpful for selection of the needle. BMI is reliable calculation for selecting needle of injection for both male and female (Holliday, 2019).

The route for drug administration through IM is injected into the vascular muscle tissue that helps for rapid absorption of the drug into blood circulation. Additionally, the absorption of drug through dorsogluteal route may be slow than the other sites of administration. And this may lead to risk of drug overdose (Dougherty and Lister 2015).

The IM injections are major part of drug administration in nursing procedures and used in almost half of country. Therefore, there are some wrong practices performed by nurses during IM injection without following any guidelines. An unsafe practice of injection decreases the effectiveness of medication and increases the risk of injury to the patient. However, the importance is to assess the IM injection protocol before the administration (Hassnein and Soliman 2016).

Background

Globally, almost 12 billion medications are given through injectable route annually to improve therapeutic efficacy.

First it is necessary to know the right IM injections techniques. The good practices include the selection of the right site for IM injection properly. Secondly, if the practices of IM injection are poor it creates pain, irritation, contracture, necrosis and muscle contracture. The best site for injection is ventrogluteal (Arslan and Özden, 2018).

In developing countries the recurrent and unsafe pattern of IM is common practice in health care system. Unsafe injection procedure is most threatening health hazard. Universally, the injections administered by multiple health care professionals like doctors, nurses and paramedics, informal providers, and quacks at different places. Quacks give illegal administration just to earn money not to provide benefit to the patient (Gyawali, Rathore et al., 2016).

Nationally, the practices of evaluating health care provider's compliance with standard infection control practices. The IM injection is common practice in health care settings for preventive and curative purpose. Pakistan is included in those countries where the practices of IM injection are on top. Unsafe practices cause infection, almost are 80000-160000 AIDS/HCV (AL-Rawajfah and Tubaishat, 2017).

It is important to improve good nursing IM injection skills that enhance the nursing practices. Appropriate clinical procedures as well as good communication skills are important part of Nurses job. Moreover, the effective practices of nurses minimize the patient discomforts and prevent complications (Prabhakaran, Ljuhar et al., 2018).

Problem Statement

IM injection is a common practice for drug administration. According to Hassnein (2016), there are some wrong practices performed by nurses during IM injection without following any guidelines. I am willing to conduct study on "Assessment of Nurses Practices regarding IM injection to cover the gaps in previous studies like small simple size, lack of knowledge regarding IM injection techniques, unsafe practices of IM injection. So, this study will improve the nurse's knowledge and psychomotor skills at clinical setting.

Research Question

The research question of this study was what are the nurses practices regarding IM injection?

Significance of the study

The study significance was to assess and improve the nurse's practices of IM injection. This study improved the nurse's knowledge and psychomotor skills at clinical

setting. This research enhanced evidence based practices. This study also helped for me as a researcher because it improved my knowledge of observational research and practice techniques that increased my worth as a researcher. This study was beneficent for my mother institute because institutional requirements will fulfilled as they produce scholars. In my clinical setting, this study was conducted first time. This study might be useful for further researcher as a baseline data who will conduct study on IM injection.

Research Objectives

To observe the nurses practices of IM injection and proper guidelines follow.

Literature Review

Hand hygiene for injection administration

Cross sectional study was conducted by Mahadeo to investigate the practices of hand hygiene among nursing staff at tertiary care hospital in Karad. Study sample was included in this study and there were 100 nurses including staff nurses and student nurses. Convenient sampling technique was used in this study. WHO hand hygiene questionnaire for health care provider was also used in this study. Assess of the five dimensions of hand hygiene includes 1.) Hand hygiene in healthcare setting. 2.) The effectiveness of hand hygiene techniques. 3.) The hand hygiene and infection control policies. 4.) The professional and organizational barriers, 5.) The strategies to improve compliance of hand hygiene. 70% of nurses practicing on first dimension, 73 % nurses were practicing on second dimension effectively, 91% nurses working effectively on third dimension, 88% nurses were practicing on fourth and 93% nurses practicing efficiently on fifth dimension of hand hygiene. This study suggest that knowledge and attitude of study participants were appropriate but there was need of improving and practice of intramuscular injection at teaching hospital that will be helpful in improving hand hygiene which minimize the risk of cross transmission of infection from nurses to patient (Shinde, 2014).

Anatomical safe site for intramuscular injection

Another cross sectional study was conducted to observe the practices of anatomically safer intramuscular injection site in Japan in 2017-2018. The study sample was 27 participants between the age of 17-30. When giving the intramuscular injection to the patient, the health care provider select the safer site for administration of injection as distance from large blood vessels, away from nerve

and bone to prevent from injury, abscess, tenderness and invasion of other pathogens that cause infection. Participants voluntarily participate in this study. The thickness of muscle was observed by the inserting 14G needle. The safer site for intramuscular injection was observed in the thigh. The p value was $P = .0052$. This study includes some limitations like small sample size, limited age group. Further studies need to perform on large scale (Nakajima, Y., 2020).

Selection of Needle insertion

Strohfus (2018) conducted a descriptive correlational study in United States to assess the evidence-based intramuscular injection techniques regarding site for injection and length of needle. An intramuscular injection questionnaire from 5-7 point Likert scale responses used in this study. Sample size was 206 nurses and LPN from health care setting and the age group was 18 to 60 year. Study data were analyzed by using SPSS, version 24. The Chi-square test was used to calculate the variations among study groups. Z-track technique was used by 61% participants. 59% respondents used ventrogluteal site for intramuscular injection and 34% participants always stretched or bunched the skin during intramuscular injection. The 53% participants were using 1-inch needle, and the 42% respondents were using 1.5-inch needle for injection administration. This study concludes that this study conducted on large scale and the results show variation according to their region and multiple health care providers included in this study. The best practice of intramuscular injection is the selection of needle according BMI.

Appropriate Angle for Intramuscular Injection

Another study was conducted regarding appropriate intramuscular injection site and angle in Japan in 2017 to observe the nurses practices of intramuscular injection techniques. Thirty participants included in this study with their own interest above the age of 17. Informed consent was taken before study start. Four sites were examined for intramuscular injection. Ultrasonography was performed to measure the thickness of deltoid muscle, humeral artery, circumflex artery and axillary nerve. On other hand the depth of needle insertion at this site was 5 mm greater than thickness of subcutaneous at the angle of 90 degree. Probe compression was avoided against skin and hold injection at 90 degree. This is appropriate angle for needle insertion and sufficient to penetrate drug into tissues in both gender male and female. Data was statistically analyzed by using the Kruskal-Wallis and Steel-Dwass tests. Thickness of muscle was analyzed by ANOVA and T-test. The significant difference was considered at $P < 0.05$. Study limitations include the

small sample size. Further studies should be conducted on single dose at the site of injection because multiple doses may cause ineffectiveness and injury (Nakajima, 2017).

Preparation of Skin before Injection Administration

Qamar (2015) conducted a cross sectional study to know the knowledge, attitudes and practices of skin preparation among the healthcare professionals. A validated, pre-designed, well-structured questionnaire was used to assess the psychomotor practices of skin preparation. The sampling technique was used the universal sampling technique. 150 participants included in this of both gender. The scoring range of the questionnaire was +5 (maximum) to -5 (minimum). The collected data was analyzed by using SPSS version-16 and the results were explored in term of percentages. Most of the respondents in this study were practicing that not using alcohol swab, cannot save time but it was necessary practice. Using just alcohol swab but not with water and soap. Participants respond that sterilizing the skin before injection administration minimizes the risks of infection. This study shows that level of knowledge regarding intramuscular injection in nurses and internes is better than medical students. Sufficient knowledge is necessary for better practices of intramuscular injection.

Gap Analysis

Previous studies which conducted on the assessment of nurse's practice regarding intramuscular injection involve gapes in their studies. Some studies had less generalizability due to small sample size. Other studies represent that knowledge of participants was adequate but practices were insufficient. Some studies explore the study findings on very large scale which is less effective. Another study show that knowledge and attitude of study participants were appropriate but there was need of improving and practice of intramuscular injection at teaching hospital that will be helpful in improving hand hygiene which minimize the risk of cross transmission of infection from nurses to patient.

Design

An observational study was conducted to assess the nurses' practices of IM injection. The study setting was Tertiary Care hospital in Lahore city.

Sample and Data Collection

To collect the sample for this study convenient sampling

technique was used. The target population of my study was 250 registered nurses and student nurses from clinical area. Study population was 156 registered nurses and sample size calculated 111 by using online Raosoft formula and 45 student nurses and their sample size also calculated 41, by using online Raosoft formula. The study participants were 156 in which 111 registered nurses and 41 student nurses. Hair, J., (2010) explore that the sample size should be more than 100 or more. The maximum sample size minimize the risk of over lifting data. Data was collected through observational checklist of nurses' psychomotor skills. The data collected from registered nurses and student nurses of two tertiary care hospitals Lahore.

Instruments and measures

An observational checklist to assess the practices of nurses regarding Intramuscular injection was used in this study. Data measured by using cut of as Scoring system for the observational checklists was a scored as correct (1 point) or incorrect (0 points). There were no items left blank. According to (El-Demerdash, 2015) if the scoring will be 65-100 it will be consider correct practices and if score will less than 65, practices will consider incorrect.

Statistical analyses

The software was used to process the data, which is IBM (SPSS) Statistical Package for Social Sciences for window, version 25. Sci-square test was used to check the association between practices of registered nurses and student nurses regarding intramuscular injection administration.

RESULTS

Demographic Data

Participants of this study was included 50% between the age of 24-29 year, 25% are 30-34 year of age, 15% are 35-40 and only 9.6% nurses included between the age of 41-45 year of age. Female nurses with the percentage of 98.1% and 1.9% male nurses participate in this study. 99.4% were charge nurses and 0.6% was head nurses. Majority of nurses participated in this study were diploma holder (85.3%), 13.5% nurses were degree holder and 1.3% were certified nurses.

Observational study includes finding of patient details which observed for practices of intramuscular injection administration. IM injection given to the 91.7% female and 8.3% were male. Height of 100% patients measured and weight also measured for 100% patients. BMI calculated for 100% patients. IM vaccination given to the

Table 1. Participants Responses about Demographic Data

S#	Responses	Percentage
1.	Age	
	a.24-29	50%
	b.30-34	25%
	c.35-40 d.41-45	15%
2.	Gender	
	a. Male	1.9%
3.	Designation	
	b. Female	98.1%
4.	Qualification	
	a. Charge Nurse	99.4%
	b. Student Nurses	0.6%
	a. Certificate	1.3%
	b. Diploma	85.3%
	c. Degree	13.5%

Table 2. Observational Responses of Participants

Participants Responses of Patient Details about IM injection			
S#	Statement	Responses	Percentage
1.	Female	a. yes	91.7%
		b. no	8.3%
2.	Height	a. yes	100%
		b. no	0.0%
3.	Weight	a. yes	100%
		b. no	0.0%
4.	Calculate BMI	a. yes	100%
		b. no	0.0%
5.	Vaccination	a. yes	6.4%
		b. no	92.9%
6.	Tolerated procedure: well (5), fairly well (4), some anxiety (3), anxiety (2), medical assistance (1)	a. yes	92.3%
		b. no	7.7%

Table 3. Provide table legend

Participants Responses of Clinician Process about IM injection			
S#	Statement	Responses	Percentage
1.	Preps the site with an alcohol wipe and allows it to dry.	a. yes	71.8%
		b. no	28.2%
2.	Controls the limb with the non-dominant hand holds the needle an inch from the skin and inserts it quickly at the 90o for IM.	a. yes	67.9%
		b. no	32.1%
3.	Injects vaccine using steady pressure; withdraws needle at angel of insertion.	a. yes	94.9%
		b. no	5.1%
4.	Applies gentle pressure to injection site for several seconds with a dry cotton ball.	a. yes	71.2%
		b. no	28.8%
5.	5 rights of administration (patient, medication, dose, time, route)	a. yes	93.0%
		b. no	7.0%
6.	Comfort measures and post-procedure instructions	a. yes	78.2%
		b. no	21.8%

6.4% patients and other intramuscular injection administered to the 92.9% patients. Table 3

Participants responses for clinical process of intramuscular injection represent that 71.8% participants

prepare the site of injection with an alcohol wipe and allows it to dry but 28.2% participants did not performed this practice. 67.9% participant's controls the limb with the non-dominant hand holds the needle an inch from the

Table 4. Intramuscular Injection Techniques among Registered Nurses and Student Nurses Cross tabulation

Clinical Activities	Nurses	Correct	Incorrect	Total	P-value
Hand Hygiene	RN	95	20	115	0.000
	SN	10	31	41	
Needle Size selected	RN	113	2	115	0.000
	SN	21	20	41	
Site Selected	RN	111	4	115	0.000
	SN	7	34	41	
Angle of insertion	RN	111	4	115	0.000
	SN	12	29	41	
Skin bunched or stretched	RN	110	5	115	0.000
	SN	8	33	41	
Needle inserted fully	RN	113	2	115	0.000
	SN	12	29	41	
Locate anatomical landmarks specific for IM injection: Palpate landmark(3), visualizes landmark (2), no observable land marking (1)	RN	114	1	115	0.000
	SN	21	20	41	

skin and inserts it quickly at the 90o for IM and 32.1% participants follow this step. 94.9% study participants injects vaccine using steady pressure; withdraws needle at angle of insertion. Gentle pressure applies to injection site for several seconds with a dry cotton ball by 71.2% participants. 93.0% participants follow the five rights of drug administration. 78.2% participants give the comfort measures and post-procedure instructions to the patients.

Holistic View of Study Finding

The statistical strong significant association was found between registered nurses and student nurses about intramuscular injection administration by using chi-square test. The clinical activities observed between registered nurses and student nurses which includes following hand hygiene 66.9%, correct practices of needle size selection was 85.4%, the site selection for intramuscular injection was 75.2%, the angle of needle insertion was correct 78.3%, skin bunched or stretched was observed correct 75.25, 79.6% practices were correct regarding needle insert fully and locate the anatomical landmarks were 86.1%. Comparatively student nurses have lack of knowledge and incorrect practices than registered nurses. P value of variables was $p = .000$. The patient details including gender, height, weight, BMI, vaccination and tolerated procedure were collected correctly by registered nurses and student nurses. The clinical procedure of nurse's practices was also observed.

DISCUSSION

The current study finding indicates the strong association

between registered nurses and student nurses. The 66.9% nurses perform hand hygiene before injection administration. As like another study conducted at Sweden represent that majority of nurses perform hand hygiene practice. P value of study findings were $p = 0.01$. They follow written policies for improving hand hygiene and to reduce the infection.

In my study most of participants (71.8%) prepares the site of injection with an alcohol wipe and allows it to dry. The aim is to minimize the risk of infection and only 28.2% did not perform this practice before administration of intramuscular injection. These results supported by the study conducted by (Birhanu. D.,2018) at Ethiopia regarding injection safety. The most of study participants have good knowledge for prevention of infection and correct practices regarding skin preparation for injection administration. $P = 0.000$, and the level of education was statistically associated with knowledge and practice regarding injection safety among nurses.

My study indicates the significant results of correct practices of selecting site for intramuscular injection administration. 75.2% nurses perform correct practices regarding site selection for IM injection. Another study explore that most of study participants select site and position for injection administration according to the physique of patient. However the skinfold thickness is different at different site and position. Average physique patients recommended for Hochstetter site for intramuscular injection (Tanioka, T., 2018).

Study findings reveal that nurse practices of skin bunched or stretched during intramuscular injection administration was observed. Most of study participants (75.2%) were performing correct practices regarding skin stretching. Only few nurses (24.2%) nurses were performing incorrect practices related to skin stretching. Similar study conducted by Salari, M., (2018) explore that

performing skin stretching or skin traction during intramuscular injection administration can significantly decrease in pain. It is effective technique of intramuscular injection administration. Mean and standard deviation was 0.75 ± 1.17 . The statistically significance was 0.001.

The study findings explore that majority of nurses performing correct practices regarding selecting needle size while administering intramuscular injection. 85.4% nurses correctly perform this technique and only 14.0% student nurses did not perform this technique accurately. The study conducted related to intramuscular injection in United States and the results compared. In their study the most of study participants select needle size before injecting injection according to site of injection. Mostly 77% select 1 inch needle, 66% study participants performing correct practices and other performing incorrect practices with the significance level of $p < .000$ (Strohufus, 2018).

CONCLUSION

The study finding reveals that IM injection practices is most commonly used in health care system. The student nurses have poor knowledge and practice if IM injection then registered nurses in clinical setting. There is need to increase the students' knowledge regarding intramuscular injection and improve their practices.

Limitation of study

Due to small sample size the results of my study cannot be generalized. Secondly, it was short time duration for study.

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